

Early Course Recommendation for Higher Education using HITS and SVD

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Informational tools for student course success in higher education are of interest to students, instructors, and administrators. In particular, course ranking and recommendation provides useful information for stakeholders in student course success. Further, users of such decision support tools would greatly benefit from understanding the general reasoning behind proposed models. General understanding of the models allows users to offer insights from their perspective and resolve sub-optimal suggestions. As student academic performance in the first year has compounding consequences for students and institutes, optimal selection of first year courses is important. To this end, we propose novel adaptations of an intuitive simple graph (network) model to extract information from student course interactions and rank courses for recommendation in the second semester of the first year. The proposed models are adapted from Hyperlink-Induced Topic Search (HITS) relating to singular value decomposition (SVD) models through the use of the first dominant right singular vector. Thus, our model may provide additional intuition for related models. Further, we find that our best HITS model outperforms an SVD model from the literature despite using far fewer singular vectors. Finally, we use ideas from the HITS models to construct a better SVD model outperforming all considered models.

1. INTRODUCTION

Student course success is essential to second semester and second year persistence (Barr, 2007). Further, student course success contributes to the decision of persisting, in that, grade distributions and course success rates are lower for students who did not persist to the second semester or second year (Barr, 2007). Additionally, course selection has an effect on student course success and student persistence as perceived course difficulty, time management, and disinterest are cited factors that affect student dropout (Kinnunen and Malmi, 2006; Xenos et al., 2002; Aldowah et al., 2020). The importance of targeted intervention in the first year relates to the fact that “the greatest attrition tends to occur between the freshman and sophomore years” (Murtaugh et al., 1999). Therefore, it is important to target retention efforts in the first year.

Student course success is related to retention rates and graduation rates, two common benchmarks for assessing performance in higher education. Thus, higher educational institutes have an

interest in improving successful completion of courses and the related metrics. State-allocated funding or bonus funding may depend on these metrics under performance based funding models and lower graduation rates have been determined to have a high societal cost (Alshehri, 2016; Schneider and Yin, 2011). Therefore, increasing student course success is important in receiving funding, attracting students, and producing societal economic benefits.

Decision support systems and rule-based expert systems have been proposed to help academic advisors support students with enhanced decision making (Almutawah, 2014; Engin et al., 2014). Further, course planning has been shown to relate to time to degree completion and graduation GPA, and data-driven methods for course selection have been proposed (Morsy and Karypis, 2019a; Thanh-Nhan et al., 2016). Thus, course recommender systems could be useful decision support tools for academic advisors.

Recommender systems have found use in many applications and have “developed in parallel to the web” (Bobadilla et al., 2013). Two systems proposed for webpage ranking are Hypertext-Induced Topic Search (HITS) and PageRank (Kleinberg, 1999; Page et al., 1999). PageRank and HITS are popular in ranking tasks and are “citational blockbusters” amassing many thousands of citations (Franceschet, 2011). While PageRank has been considered in the literature for course recommendation tasks, HITS has not been investigated for course recommendation tasks. We further note that the many possible adjustments to search engine ranking methods discussed in Langville and Meyer (2012), such as the use of different voting strategies, have not been considered for course recommendation.

Research on course recommendation for second semester courses is sparse and when it appears it is subsumed by the typical use of n semesters for the $n + 1$ semester recommendation. Cold-start problems, where no or very little course information exists, have attracted some attention for massive open online course (MOOC) recommendation (Jing and Tang, 2017; Piao and Breslin, 2016). Cold-start and non-cold-start problems are also considered for traditional next-semester grade prediction (Sweeney et al., 2015; Sweeney et al., 2016). Second semester course recommendation using the first semester course performance is between a cold-start problem and the typical consideration of ensuring a sufficient number of semesters for recommendation. However, course recommendation in the second semester may have the most impact due to the compounding consequences of first year performance. Thus, we target course recommendation in the second semester.

Evaluation of offline-recommender systems, especially for course recommendation, can be tricky. Students only select a small number of courses each semester compared to the large number of offered courses. Also, some courses may be required for a student’s major so that the selection of some courses is guaranteed. For required courses, only the time a course is taken and the grade awarded for the course are variable. We note that few required courses are taken in the first year due to flexibility in selecting elective and general education courses. The large number of possible courses and few selected courses leads to highly sparse data (Polyzou and Karypis, 2016). Additionally, only a student’s grade in a course is given as opposed to information about student interest. This raises questions such as “does an A in a course mean the course was a good recommendation?” or “does a C- in a course mean the course was a bad recommendation?” and the answer would be dependent on the lens for evaluating the recommendations, e.g. knowledge gained, student interest, good performance, etc. Recall and precision metrics utilize relevant recommendations which may be interpreted in some cases as selection of an item or in other cases as selection of an item along with a good rating for the item. In Morsy and Karypis (2019b), the authors develop a *recall(good)* and *recall(bad)* metric where good implies the grade

awarded in the courses was at or above the student’s historical average GPA and bad implies the grade awarded was below the student’s historical average GPA. We utilize *recall(good)* and *recall(bad)* as in [Morsy and Karypis \(2019b\)](#) but also consider metrics *recall(pass)* and *recall(fail)* where pass implies the grade awarded in the course was at or above a grade of C and fail implies the course grade was below a grade of C.

We identify the following contributions of this research:

1. The consideration of the problem of second semester course recommendation.
2. The validation of SVD(++), SVD(+/-), and SVD(+) models discussed in [Morsy and Karypis \(2019b\)](#).
3. The construction and explanation of HITS course recommenders.
4. A demonstration of the importance of matrix construction with CourseHITSW(+/-) outperforming SVD(+/-) now referred to as SVD-GB(+/-) for its construction using good and bad subsequent courses and to distinguish it from the new SVD models.
5. An improvement to SVD-GB(+/-) by constructing the count matrices with respect to pass/fail, SVD-PF(+/-), instead of good/bad. Also, a further improvement, SVD-SPF(+/-), to the SVD-PF(+/-) model by using the scaling used for CourseHITSW.
6. A comparison of the *recall(good)* and *recall(bad)* metrics discussed in [Morsy and Karypis \(2019b\)](#) with *recall(pass)* and *recall(fail)* metrics.
7. Practical logic for filtering courses before recommendation to avoid recommending courses approximately above or below the student’s current academic standing.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the related work for course recommendation, search engine ranking methods, and SVD in educational data mining. Section 3 describes our adapted HITS course recommenders. Section 4 describes our experiment framework and course filtering. Then, we present results in Section 5 and discuss the results and conclusions in Section 6.

2. RELATED WORK

The problem of course recommendation fits into the broader subject of recommendation systems with the two primary models being that of “prediction” and “ranking” ([Aggarwal, 2016](#)). Course recommendation appears in the literature as top-n course recommendation and course grade/rating prediction. We note that course grade prediction also lends itself to course recommendation as courses can be recommended based on the predicted grade. The problem of grade prediction and top-n course recommendation is handled in [Elbadrawy and Karypis \(2016\)](#) where the top-n recommendation uses a popularity-based scheme and the grade prediction uses an average of neighboring student grades. Course rating prediction is given in [Bakhshinategh et al. \(2017\)](#) where a course recommender based on graduating attributes, defined as “attributes that describe the developing values of the student,” was considered utilizing collaborative filtering, a similarity metric, and student nearest-neighbor considerations extending recommendation/prediction tasks to factors other than grade. While there are many possibilities for course

ranking and recommendation models, we focus our review on matrix factorization methods in education data mining, specifically SVD, and the use of search engine ranking methods for ranking and recommendation tasks.

Search engine ranking methods have been used for educational data mining and recommender system problems. [London and Németh \(2014\)](#) adapted PageRank to rank students based on their end of year grades in shared classes and discovered the rankings correlated with the rankings by end of year grade averages but seemed to account for course difficulty. Further, [Cucuringu et al. \(2018\)](#) used PageRank to identify course sequences to infer hidden course prerequisites along with other state-of-the-art ranking methods that were in close agreement. PageRank was also used as “CourseRank” in a course search ranking system using a course-skill bipartite graph with an altered teleportation matrix ([Yao et al., 2020](#)). Markov chain methods similar to personalized PageRank have also been considered as in [Polyzou et al. \(2019\)](#) where course sequences from historical data are considered in a framework for course selection. Further, PageRank and HITS are central to the idea of link mining and link-based object ranking (LBR) relating to grade prediction using coenrollment networks which have been shown to outperform “flat” models ([Getoor and Diehl, 2005](#); [Gardner and Brooks, 2018](#); [Gardner et al., 2018](#)). While, PageRank and HITS have been considered in some contexts for educational data mining, there is much left to explore using these techniques.

More generally, search engine ranking methods have been considered successfully for other recommendation tasks. For example, Personalized PageRank was used with a tri-partite context-aware representations (user, context, item) for recommendation tasks ([Musto et al., 2021](#)). [Liu and Yang \(2008\)](#) used a method similar to PageRank for ranking movies, and the use of HITS was suggested in [Goel and Goodman \(2009\)](#) for recommending movies. A similar approach with HITS was used by [London and Csendes \(2013\)](#) to rank wine-testers by considering a bipartite graph with a set of wine-testers and a set of wines. By using the bipartite graph construction with two differing node sets, HITS has a slightly different flavor from the usual consideration of one set of webpages. More recently, HITS has been used along with association rules for mobile app recommendation [Zhong et al. \(2019\)](#) showing its recent usage in recommendation problems. As supported by the literature, HITS has some flexibility in ranking and recommendation tasks and has much room for growth in educational data mining.

The usage of matrix factorization methods is popular in the literature for educational data mining tasks. [Sweeney et al. \(2015\)](#); [Sweeney et al. \(2016\)](#) used SVD along with SVD post-processed with k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) and Factorization Machines (best performing) for next semester grade prediction. [Polyzou and Karypis \(2016\)](#) used matrix factorization for course grade prediction along with regression models. [Sorour et al. \(2015\)](#) used latent semantic analysis (LSA) utilizing SVD on a weighted word/comment co-occurrence matrix for student comments after lessons to predict student course grades. In [Morsy and Karypis \(2019b\)](#), the authors present a grade-aware course recommender for course ranking and grade prediction using singular value decomposition on course co-occurrence matrices. Recommendation was conducted using the similarity of the student’s profile computed from the historical course embeddings with the target course embeddings. The frequent usage of SVD in the literature shows its importance in educational data mining tasks.

Figure 1: A sample subgraph with its user-item matrix.

3. HITS COURSE RECOMMENDATION

3.1. COURSEHITS GRAPH CONSTRUCTION

The Hypertext-Induced Topic Search (HITS) algorithm described in [Kleinberg \(1999\)](#), alternatively called the hubs and authorities algorithm, was originally used to compute “popularity scores” for ranking web pages in accordance with search engine queries ([Langville and Meyer, 2006](#)). We propose to construct a course recommender using HITS similar to that of the applications considered in [Goel and Goodman \(2009\)](#) and [London and Csendes \(2013\)](#). We construct our course recommender by constructing a bipartite graph $G_x^z = (U_x, V_x, E_x^z)$ for each student x depending on the neighboring students $U_x \subset U$ and their respective courses $V_x \subset V$ in the target recommendation semester with an edge $(u, v) \in E_x^z$ provided that student u earned at least a course grade of $z \in [0, 4]$ in course v . Thus, we have freedom to choose how to select neighbors U_x for a student x and the minimum required grade for these neighbors to give their recommendation. We note that by considering $G^z = (U, V, E^z)$ where U is the set of all historical students and V the corresponding courses with an edge $(u, v) \in E^z$ if student u meets the minimum grade requirement of z in course v , then we get G_x^z by considering the subgraph of G^z formed by taking the vertex set $U_x = U \cap N_x$ where N_x is the set of neighboring students for x . Thus, we see that possible courses for recommendation V_x differ for each student x depending on the performance of courses taken in the target semester by similar students demonstrating the query-dependence property of HITS. An example subgraph, G_x^z , is illustrated in [Figure 1](#).

To select neighbors for a student x , we may select students with matching attributes. Specifically, we may use the college the student was admitted into (entry college) e.g. College of Business. Then, we may require a matching course with matching grade in the first semester. We require either the grade to match exactly, called exact grade matching, or the letter portion of the grade to match, called strict letter grade matching or letter grade matching. We note that a strict letter grade is simply the set of grades without plus or minus grades, that is, $A- \mapsto A$, $C+ \mapsto C$, $C \mapsto C$, etc. By selecting students from the same entry college, the students should have a similar interest and initial course path in the courses taken. Additionally, selecting students with a matching course, grade pair in the first semester should allow for selecting students

Figure 2: An illustration of neighbor selection for a student using strict letter grade matching with attributes.

with similar observed academic standing in the semester prior to the target semester. To be precise, for a student $y \in U$ we consider the set B_y of ordered pairs (c, g) called the course grade pairs for the initial semester where $c \in V$ is a course taken by y in the initial semester and $g \in \{A, A-, B+, B, B-, C+, C, C-, D+, D, F, W\}$ is the grade for the course. Then, we define the course grade neighborhood of a student x as the set $L_x = \{y \in U \mid y \neq x, B_x \cap B_y \neq \emptyset\}$. Similarly, for a student y we consider the tuple of attributes $a_y = (\text{entry college}, \dots)$ and define the attribute neighborhood of a student x as $M_x = \{y \in U \mid y \neq x, a_x = a_y\}$. Finally, we define the neighborhood using attributes of a student x to be $N_x = L_x \cap M_x$ and the neighborhood not using attributes of the student to be $N_x = L_x$. We note that there are many similarity metrics and other more sophisticated methods of selecting neighbors that can be explored. An example graphic illustrating neighbor selection with attributes by strict letter grade (letter grade matching) is given in Figure 2 where we see that students 3 and 5 are neighbors to student 1 since the entry colleges match as well as at least one course, letter grade pair whereas students 2 and 4 are missing some matching component needed to be a neighbor of student 1.

In constructing the subgraph, we have the option of varying the parameter z , the grade required to form a connection in the subgraph, so that we have recommender R_z from bipartite graph G_x^z for each possible grade value from the standard plus/minus letter grading system. We note that z can be the letter grade or its numerical equivalent. Further, we note that in our application we equate a withdrawal grade with a failing grade by $W = F \mapsto 0$ for both the neighbor selection and forming connections in the subgraph.

3.2. COURSEHITS COMPUTATION

The example bipartite graph G_x^z in Figure 1 for student x with $z = A-$ has three, $m = 3$, fictional neighbors earning at least an $A-$ in five, $n = 5$, fictional courses. We recall the corresponding user-item matrix in Figure 1 as Equation (1).

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{matrix} & c_1 & c_2 & c_3 & c_4 & c_5 \\ \begin{matrix} s_1 \\ s_2 \\ s_3 \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix} \quad (1)$$

For the HITS iterative procedure, we let the courses (authorities) for iteration i be represented by the $(n, 1)$ vector $\mathbf{c}^{(i)}$ with $\mathbf{c}^{(0)} = \mathbf{1}/n$, and the students (hubs) for iteration i be represented by the $(m, 1)$ vector $\mathbf{s}^{(i)}$ with $\mathbf{s}^{(0)} = \mathbf{1}/m$. The HITS algorithm then consists of iterating Equations (2)-(5), in order, until some stopping criteria. We note that Equations (2) and (3) correspond to the students “voting” for courses and the updated courses “voting” for students, respectively. Equations (4) and (5) correspond to normalizing the student and course vectors. The stopping criteria is either convergence in the iterates to some predefined tolerance τ , $\|\mathbf{c}^{(i)} - \mathbf{c}^{(i-1)}\| < \tau$, or the current iteration exceeds the maximum allocated iterations M , that is, $i \geq M$.

$$\mathbf{c}^{(i+1)} = \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{s}^{(i)} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{s}^{(i+1)} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{c}^{(i+1)} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{c}^{(i+1)} = \mathbf{c}^{(i+1)} / \|\mathbf{c}^{(i+1)}\|_1 \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{s}^{(i+1)} = \mathbf{s}^{(i+1)} / \|\mathbf{s}^{(i+1)}\|_1 \quad (5)$$

We note that Equation (2) and Equation (3) can be compressed and written as $\mathbf{c}^{(i+1)} = \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A} \mathbf{c}^{(i)}$ or $\mathbf{s}^{(i+1)} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{s}^{(i)}$, recognized as the power method for finding the dominant eigenvector. We remark that some researchers have suggested that as few as 10-15 iterations may be required for convergence with HITS, and PageRank may require few as 50-100 iterations for convergence (Langville and Meyer, 2006). Thus, we set the maximum allocated iterations as $M = 100$ for good measure. We note that HITS is similar to singular value decomposition (SVD) in that the eigenvectors of $\mathbf{A} \mathbf{A}^\top$ and $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ are left and right singular vectors of \mathbf{A} , respectively (Benzi et al., 2013). However, only the dominant eigenvectors of $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{A} \mathbf{A}^\top$ are used by HITS whereas a reformulation could use additional eigenvector information (Farahat et al., 2006). Further, it has been noted that each of the eigenvectors relates to “reinforcing hubs and authorities” identifying a particular community (Gibson et al., 1998). To ensure the algorithm converges to a unique solution, we use the modified HITS method described in Langville and Meyer (2006) by replacing $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$ with

$$\mathbf{M} = \xi \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A} + \frac{(1 - \xi)}{n} \mathbf{1}_{n \times n}. \quad (6)$$

We observe from the Equations (2) and (3) that hubs gain more points by being linked to weightier authorities and authorities gain more points by being linked to weightier hubs. Further, we might loosely interpreted ξ providing the convex combination of matrices in Equation (6) as

Figure 3: CourseHITS Algorithm with “voting” steps highlighted.

the proportion of time points are awarded following the structure of the graph as opposed to awarding points evenly. We note that the parameter α in PageRank is similar to the parameter ξ in HITS and α has been shown to attenuate the power law distribution of the rankings for PageRank (Chartier et al., 2011). For the modified HITS method, we still normalize after each step to obtain the new iterative procedure in Equations (7) and (4).

$$\mathbf{c}^{(i+1)} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{c}^{(i)} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{c}^{(i+1)} = \mathbf{c}^{(i+1)} / \|\mathbf{c}^{(i+1)}\|_1 \quad (4)$$

In this particular example, for $\xi = 0.9$ with convergence criteria

$$\|\mathbf{c}^{(i)} - \mathbf{c}^{(i-1)}\| < \tau = 10^{-7},$$

we have convergence in $k = 17$ iterates yielding Equation (8). Thus, we have an ordering of [Course2, Course4, Course1, Course5, Course3], ignoring the tie.

$$\mathbf{c}^{(17)} \approx \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} Course & PopularityScore \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} course1 \\ course2 \\ course3 \\ course4 \\ course5 \end{matrix} & \left(\begin{matrix} 0.2055 \\ 0.3004 \\ 0.0493 \\ 0.3004 \\ 0.1443 \end{matrix} \right) \end{matrix} \quad (8)$$

We give an illustrated version of the CourseHITS algorithm in Figure 3.

3.3. COURSEHITS LIMITATION

One solution to course recommendation to improve student course success might be to recommend courses with the highest average grade among a student’s neighbors, an “easy” recommender, like that of the baseline model MovieAvg in Cremonesi et al. (2010). Another solution might be to recommend courses that are popular among a student’s neighbors, a popular recommender, like that of the baseline model TopPop in Cremonesi et al. (2010). Both a high average course GPA and course popularity are desirable, and we might expect that either recommendation scheme should be a fairly good start for the problem of course recommendation. CourseHITS combines these solutions by computing a popularity score and requiring a cutoff grade z for edges in the bipartite graph, so that the popularity score is then computed among students and courses with a minimum grade of z . Thus, CourseHITS should account for popularity among a minimum desired grade, that is, accounting for both popularity and grade. However, we note that the recommender in this form rewards good ratings but does not penalize bad ratings, so that a popular course may overtake a course with a better grade distribution, that is, CourseHITS has a popularity bias. Thus, we must try to overcome the popular course bias in CourseHITS with CourseHITSW.

3.4. COURSEHITSW

To further modify the HITS construction to correct for the possibility of popular courses overtaking courses with better grade distributions, we can manipulate the weights of the edges in

the graph by utilizing ideas from the Markov method which has been used to successfully rank sports teams using PageRank. Langville and Meyer (2012) write that “[t]he Markov rating method can be summarized by one word: *voting*.” For HITS, when we treat the bipartite graph as a weighted directed graph, we can choose how a hub should vote for an authority and how an authority should, in turn, vote for a hub. This approach would yield the user-item matrix \mathbf{A} in Equation (1) provided we have each hub yield a vote value of 1 for linked authorities and each authority yield a vote value of 1 for linked hubs. Interestingly, when used in sports ranking, the Markov method allows for multiple votes to be cast to account for point scores or other game statistics, that is, we can combine matrices with different voting strategies, v_j , using a convex combination to weight the voting strategies to obtain:

$$\mathbf{S} = \alpha_1 \mathbf{S}_{v_1} + \alpha_2 \mathbf{S}_{v_2} + \dots + \alpha_n \mathbf{S}_{v_n}; \quad \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i = 1; \quad \alpha_j \geq 0$$

The matrix \mathbf{S} would then take the place of the user-item matrix \mathbf{A} for calculation.

CourseHITSW uses all edges between users and courses for neighbors, that is, we do not set a grade cutoff for edges in the subgraph, or equivalently, we use the edges in $G_x^{z=0}$. Then, we weight each edge using the proportion of neighboring students earning at least a grade of z for the course associated with the edge. For example, suppose that 10 neighbors of a student x took the course MATH101 in the target semester and 7 earned at least a grade of $z = A-$, then any edge to or from MATH101 in the graph would have a value of 0.7. Additionally, we can raise the proportions to some power q to increase the value separation. We will call the recommender using this voting strategy CourseHITSW to differentiate it from CourseHITS. If we let $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ be the vector of proportions for each of the courses and \mathbf{A} be the user-item matrix for $G_x^{z=0}$, then we have

$$\mathbf{W}^+ = \left(\mathbf{1} (\boldsymbol{\rho}^{\odot q})^\top \right) \odot \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A} \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\rho})^q$$

where \odot is the hadamard product (elementwise multiplication) and $\odot q$ is the q th hadamard power.

3.5. COURSEHITSW(+)

To further penalize bad ratings, we consider a construction of CourseHITSW where we compute the proportions for neighboring students earning below a grade of z yielding matrix \mathbf{W}^- . Thus, we can consider the original CourseHITSW model as CourseHITSW(+) and the model using \mathbf{W}^- as CourseHITSW(-). Then, we define CourseHITSW(+/-) as subtracting the result of CourseHITSW(-), \mathbf{c}^- , from CourseHITSW(+), \mathbf{c}^+ , that is,

$$\mathbf{c}^{+-} = \mathbf{c}^+ - \mathbf{c}^-.$$

3.6. POSSIBLE COURSEHITS EXTENSIONS

We note that the CourseHITS methods use the Gram matrix of a constructed user-item matrix \mathbf{A} . For columns \mathbf{a}_i of \mathbf{A} , the Gram matrix is given by $\mathbf{G}_{ij} = \langle \mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j \rangle$. The Gram matrix is also referred to as the kernel matrix when a kernel κ is used to form the matrix as $\mathbf{G}_{ij} = \kappa(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j)$ (Shawe-Taylor and Cristianini, 2004). We note that these concepts are related as a feature map ϕ

Figure 4: Example of $\mathbf{C}(s \rightarrow c)$, $\mathbf{B}(c \rightarrow s)$ for voting such that $\mathbf{C}^\top \neq \mathbf{B}$.

can be used so that $\mathbf{G}_{ij} = \langle \phi(\mathbf{a}_i), \phi(\mathbf{a}_j) \rangle = \kappa(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j)$ if and only if κ is positive semi-definite (Jordan, 2004). Thus, alternative feature maps and/or kernels can be explored.

Further, we note that allowing the two different node sets to vote differently may be desired. It seems the best way to preserve the structure and properties of the method given different voting strategies $\mathbf{B}_{m \times n}$ and $\mathbf{C}_{n \times m}$ is to use the matrix $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{CB}$ in the CourseHITS algorithm, continuing to computing the Gram matrix $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A}$. An illustration of non-symmetric voting is given in Figure 4. The two different node sets voting differently may be useful when considering perception and performance, that is, student perception of the course may be the student voting for the course, and student performance in the course may be the course voting for the student.

4. EXPERIMENT

4.1. COURSE FILTERING

A domain specific problem of course recommendation is that of identifying courses that should not be recommended due to unmet prerequisites or advanced academic standing, in that, we would like to avoid recommending irrelevant courses. Determining prerequisite fulfillment from a full information state, that is, knowledge of all completed courses and grades along with test scores for determining placement when first attempting a course in a subject, can be reduced to evaluating the corresponding Boolean expressions from the course catalog. We mined the course catalog corresponding to the data for non-major specific Boolean expressions. Due to dataset limitations, we lack the full information state for determining prerequisites as students may bring in courses through a variety of pre-enrollment college credit options such as advanced placement and dual enrollment, and we only have knowledge of courses taken in the first year semesters.

To simplify the problem of determining prerequisite fulfillment and courses below a student's current academic standing with partial information, we consider the prerequisite Boolean

expression B_c for a course $c \in C$, consisting of courses $P_c \subset C$, grouping symbols, the logical connectives \vee and \wedge , or an empty expression, so that $B_c \rightarrow c$. As prerequisite courses are needed for the target course, by taking a target course it may be assumed to imply that the student has academic standing above that of the prerequisite courses, so that $c \rightarrow P_c$. Thus, to determine courses below the current level of academic standing, we recursively find prerequisites of the courses taken in the initial semesters using Algorithm 1 in Figure 5.

Then, to check prerequisite fulfillment, we create a vector of Booleans initialized to false where the dimensions are the courses C ordered alphabetically. We then set each of the recursively found “below current standing” prerequisites to true and additionally set the courses taken in the initial semester to true provided a passing grade was earned. With this boolean vector, we evaluate prerequisite expressions for each course to determine if a student is approximately eligible to take the course, and further, the boolean vector, where true, identifies courses not to recommend for being approximately below the current standing. This approach has an observed limitation in that a few courses list many math courses, joined by logical disjunction, as a prerequisite which will cause all of these courses to be assumed as being below the current academic standing which may not be the case and cause the recommender to avoid recommending math courses. Similarly, there are a few instances where an introductory science course and lab is required but the specific pair does not matter, so that by taking a course with these prerequisites all of the introductory science classes are assumed to be taken. Overall, this approach strikes a balance between simplicity and functionality while avoiding messy and complicated edge cases with potentially limited returns for improvement. An illustration of the course filtering method for recommendation is given in Figure 5.

4.2. DATA

The data used to conduct the experiment consists of student attribute and student course data for first-time-in-college (FTIC) students, who attended the fall and spring semesters of the first year, at a regional university for the years 2015-2018. In total, there are 5320 students in the dataset and 805 unique courses. Further, students (who attended both semesters) took an average of 4.74 courses in the first semester and 4.73 courses in the second semester. The student attribute data used includes an assigned identifier and the student’s entry college. A generalized representation of the attribute data is given in Table 1. The attribute data is used to select appropriate neighbors

Table 1: The general format of the student attribute dataset.

ID	Entry College
100	Humanities
101	Sciences
102	Business
103	Business
104	Education
105	Education
⋮	⋮

from which to recommend first-year second-semester courses.

Figure 5: The process of determining courses to allow for recommendation when deciding to filter courses.

The student course data consists of the courses the students took in the fall and spring semesters of the first year along with their grades. A generalized representation of the data is given in Table 2.

Table 2: The general format of the student course dataset.

ID	Cohort Year	Semester	Course	Grade
100	2017	Fall	MATH101	A
100	2017	Fall	BIO101	B
100	2017	Spring	BIO102	B+
101	2018	Fall	ART101	A-
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

The data for the filter (filter data), for prerequisites and determining course standing, mined from the corresponding course catalog with the “Implies” column generated by Algorithm 1 in Figure 5, in its general form is given in Table 3. Each course in Table 3 has a prerequisite expression in the “Condition” column where we replace, in the expression, the courses in the “Replace” column with true or false depending on if the course was passed or if the course is implied by taking another course. Further, the “Implies” column in Table 3 lists the courses that can be implied by taking the course in the “Course” column. Further, using Algorithm 4 in Figure 5, we obtain the pre-computed courses to filter out displayed in Table 4.

4.3. EVALUATION

There are many interesting ways to evaluate properties of course recommender systems such as serendipity (Pardos and Jiang, 2020). Our analysis will focus on using the ideas of $Recall(good)$, $Recall(bad)$, and $Recall(diff)$ metrics described in Morsy and Karypis (2019b). In Morsy and Karypis (2019b), the authors consider a good (subsequent) course to be a course where a student earned at or above his/her prior average grade; otherwise, the course is considered a bad (subsequent) course. In our paper, we use the same $Recall(good/bad/diff)$ metrics but also define $Recall(pass/fail/diff)$ where a passed (subsequent) course is a course for which a student received a grade at or above a certain threshold which we will set to 2.0 corresponding to a C grade; otherwise, the course is considered a failed subsequent course. We denote $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ as the difference between $Recall(good)$ and $Recall(bad)$, and $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ as the difference between $Recall(pass)$ and $Recall(fail)$. We average the results from the student test set to obtain the average (avg) $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ and $Recall(diff)_{pf}$. Additionally, we use the *Matched* metric to evaluate the number of courses that were recommended and matched the student’s taken courses

Table 3: The general format for the filter data.

Course	Condition	Replace	Implies
ACCT101		[]	[]
ACCT102	ACCT101	[ACCT101]	[ACCT101]
ACCT103	ACCT102 & (and) FIN101	[ACCT102, FIN101]	[ACCT102, ACCT101, FIN101]
ART101			
ART102	ART101 (or) CER101	[ART101, CER101]	[ART101, CER101]
ART103	(ART102) (ART101 & CER101)	[ART102, ART101, CER101]	[ART102, ART101, CER101]
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

Table 4: The general format of the precomputed filter data.

ID	Filter
100	[BIO102, ART102, MATH103, MATH401, ...]
101	[CHM102, BIO102, CHM301, LAW401, ...]
⋮	⋮

and compute the total of the matched courses for the student test set. The evaluation metrics are summarized in Equations 9 - 17.

$$Recall(good) = \frac{|\{\text{Student Good Courses}\} \cap \{\text{Recommended}\}|}{|\{\text{Student Good Courses}\}|} \quad (9)$$

$$Recall(bad) = \frac{|\{\text{Student Bad Courses}\} \cap \{\text{Recommended}\}|}{|\{\text{Student Bad Courses}\}|} \quad (10)$$

$$Recall(pass) = \frac{|\{\text{Student Passed Courses}\} \cap \{\text{Recommended}\}|}{|\{\text{Student Passed Courses}\}|} \quad (11)$$

$$Recall(fail) = \frac{|\{\text{Student Fail Courses}\} \cap \{\text{Recommended}\}|}{|\{\text{Student Fail Courses}\}|} \quad (12)$$

$$Recall(diff)_{gb} = Recall(good) - Recall(bad) \quad (13)$$

$$Recall(diff)_{pf} = Recall(pass) - Recall(fail) \quad (14)$$

$$avg\ Recall(diff)_{gb/pf} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Recall(diff)_{gb/pf} \text{ for test student } i}{n}. \quad (15)$$

$$Matched = |\{\text{Student Taken Courses}\} \cap \{\text{Recommended}\}| \quad (16)$$

$$\text{total } Matched = \sum_{i=1}^n Matched \text{ for test student } i \quad (17)$$

We note that any further mention of $recall(diff)_{gb/pf}$ is in reference to average $recall(diff)_{gb/pf}$ and $Matched$ to total $Matched$. Since the train/test split is set to 90%/10%, we have $n = 532$. Further, the results present the value of the metric further averaged over 10 repeats of the experiment (with different train/test realizations).

We note that the recommended courses are the top ten courses from the course recommender.

4.4. COMPETING MODELS

4.4.1. CourseAvg

The “easy” recommender, CourseAvg, sorts courses in descending order by the course average GPA for the neighborhood given “enough” students took the course in the target semester. By requiring enough students to have taken the course in the target semester, we avoid recommending courses with a high average grade but with few observed instances.

4.4.2. CoursePop

The popular recommender, CoursePop, sorts courses in descending order by the number of students in the neighborhood who have taken the course in the target semester and has no additional parameters.

4.4.3. SVD Recommenders

We utilize the SVD Recommender model from [Morsy and Karypis \(2019b\)](#) as SVD_{gb} . Further, we develop the model SVD_{pf} where the count matrices use counts of course j above a certain grade threshold. Let $n(z)_{ij}^+ = n_{ij}^+$ be the number of students who have taken course i before j and course j had grade $\geq z$. Further, let $n(z)_{ij}^- = n_{ij}^-$ be the number of students who have taken course i before course j and course j had grade $< z$. Then, we have co-occurrence matrices:

- $\mathbf{F}^+ = n_{ij}^+$
- $\mathbf{F}^- = n_{ij}^-$
- $\mathbf{F}^{+-} = \mathbf{F}^+ - \mathbf{F}^-$
- $\mathbf{F}^{++} = \mathbf{F}^+ + \mathbf{F}^-$

Then, we proceed as in [Morsy and Karypis \(2019b\)](#). We let $\mathbf{X}_{n \times m}$ be one of the co-occurrence matrices \mathbf{F}^{+-} , \mathbf{F}^+ , and \mathbf{F}^{++} with the rows scaled using the $L1$ norm. Then, we compute the truncated SVD of $\mathbf{X}_{n \times m} = \mathbf{U}_{n \times d} \mathbf{S}_{d \times d} \mathbf{V}_{d \times m}^\top = \mathbf{U}_d \mathbf{S}_d \mathbf{V}_d^\top$. Further, the previous and subsequent course embeddings are given as $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{U}_d \sqrt{\mathbf{S}_d}$ and $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{V}_d \sqrt{\mathbf{S}_d}$, respectively.

Now, to recommend for a student s , we let $\mathbf{a}_{1 \times n}^\top$ be such that $a_{1,i} = 1$, if student s has taken course i prior to the target semester and $a_{1,i} = 0$, otherwise. Then, the profile of student s is given as $\mathbf{p}^\top = \mathbf{a}^\top \mathbf{H}$. Finally, we compute the ratings of the target courses $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{T} \mathbf{p}$. To recommend the top- k courses, we sort \mathbf{r} in descending order and take the top- k target courses.

We note that the methods $SVD_{pf}(+-)$, $SVD_{pf}(+)$, $SVD_{pf}(++)$ correspond to the count matrices \mathbf{F}^{+-} , \mathbf{F}^+ , \mathbf{F}^{++} , respectively.

Additionally, we consider the models $SVD_{spf}(+-)$, $SVD_{spf}(+)$, $SVD_{spf}(++)$ where we scale the count matrices using the scaling from CourseHITSW. We replace \mathbf{F}^+ with $\mathbf{F}^+ \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{\geq z})^q$ and \mathbf{F}^- with $\mathbf{F}^- \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{< z})^q$.

5. RESULTS

5.1. PARAMETER ANALYSIS

First, we find the best parameters for each model discussed. We use exact grade matching without attributes for the neighborhood strategy. Further, we require a minimum neighbor count of 30 for a recommendation to be made. Also, we do not apply the course filter. Each parameter experiment is repeated ten times, and the results are averaged. The following subsections detail the recommenders and their parameter variations.

Table 5: CourseAvg Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Values
count	c	[0, 10, 25, 50, 100, 200, 400]

5.1.1. CourseAvg Recommender

CourseAvg has one parameter, the required student course count c . Table 5 shows the evaluated values for the parameters of CourseAvg.

The best CourseAVG models from the parameter analysis with respect to $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ and $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ are given in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

5.1.2. CoursePop Recommender

CoursePop has no parameters as it simply sorts the target courses by popularity (enrollment). We include CoursePop in the results of the parameter analysis in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

5.1.3. CourseHITS Recomender

The CourseHITS model has two parameters we may wish to vary. The grade parameter for creating the user-item matrix varies among the numerical values (\mathcal{N}) of the different letter grades (\mathcal{L}) characterized by the map f with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} &= \{A, A-, B+, B, B-, C+, C, C-, D+, D, F, W\} \\ \mathcal{N} &= \{4.0, 3.7, 3.3, 3.0, 2.7, 2.3, 2.0, 1.7, 1.3, 1.0, 0.0\} \\ \text{where } f &: \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \mathcal{N} \text{ and } f(W) = 0.0 \end{aligned}$$

so that we have a CourseHITS recommender H_x for each $x \in \mathcal{N}$. Further, the teleportation parameter varies for $0 < \xi < 1$, so we consider values in [0.1, 0.2, . . . 0.9].

We fix the convergence criteria parameters as $M = 100$ for the maximum allocated iterations and $\tau = 10^{-5}$ for the convergence tolerance. Table 6 summarizes the evaluated values for the parameters of CourseHITS.

Table 6: CourseHITS Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Values
Max Iterations	M	100
Convergence Tolerance	τ	10^{-5}
Required Rating	z	[4.0, 3.7, 3.3, 3.0, 2.7, 2.3, 2.0, 1.7, 1.3, 1.0, 0.0]
Teleportation	ξ	[0.1, 0.2, . . . , 0.9]

The best CourseHITS models from the parameter analysis with respect to $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ and $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ are given in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

Figure 6: Impact of ξ and z for CourseHITSW(+/-) model with $q = 1$

5.1.4. CourseHITSW Recommenders

The CourseHITSW recommenders use the parameters from the CourseHITS recommenders with additional parameters for the variation of CourseHITSW used, either + or +-, and the power applied to the proportion vectors. Table 7 summarizes the evaluated values for the parameters of CourseHITSW.

Table 7: CourseHITSW Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Values
Max Iterations	M	100
Convergence Tolerance	τ	10^{-5}
Required Rating	z	[4.0, 3.7, 3.3, 3.0, 2.7, 2.3, 2.0, 1.7, 1.3, 1.0, 0.0]
Teleportation	ξ	[0.1, 0.2, ..., 0.9]
Variation	v	[+, +-]
Power	q	[1, 2, 3, 4]

The best CourseHITSW models from the parameter analysis with respect to $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ and $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ are given in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

We examine the impact of ξ and z for CourseHITSW(+/-) with $q = 1$ with respect to $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ in Figure 6.

5.1.5. SVD-GB

The SVD_{gb} (SVD-GB) model has parameter d for the truncated SVD with rank d and parameter v for the variation of the co-occurrence matrix used. Table 8 summarizes the evaluated values for the parameters of SVD-GB.

Table 8: SVD-GB Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Values
Variation	v	[+-, +, ++]
Rank	d	[1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 30, 50, 100, 200, 400]

The best SVD-GB models from the parameter analysis with respect to $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ and $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ are given in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

5.1.6. SVD-PF

The SVD_{pf} (SVD-PF) model has the same parameters as SVD_{gb} with additional parameter z for the required grade for splitting the counts into the + and - counts. Table 9 summarizes the evaluated values for the parameters of SVD-PF.

Table 9: SVD-PF Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Values
Variation	v	[+-, +, ++]
Rank	d	[1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 30, 50, 100, 200, 400]
Required Rating	z	[4.0, 3.7, 3.3, 3.0, 2.7, 2.3, 2.0, 1.7, 1.3, 1.0, 0.0]

The best SVD-PF models from the parameter analysis with respect to $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ and $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ are given in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

5.1.7. SVD-SPF

The SVD_{spf} (SVD-SPF) model has the same parameters as SVD_{pf} with additional parameter k for the power applied to the proportion vectors used for scaling. Table 10 summarizes the evaluated values for the parameters of SVD-SPF.

Table 10: SVD-SPF Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Values
Variation	v	[+-, +, ++]
Rank	d	[1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 30, 50, 100, 200, 400]
Required Rating	z	[4.0, 3.7, 3.3, 3.0, 2.7, 2.3, 2.0, 1.7, 1.3, 1.0, 0.0]
Power	q	[1, 2, 3, 4]

The best SVD-SPF models from the parameter analysis with respect to $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ and $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ are given in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

We examine the impact of d and z for SVD-SPF(+-) using $q = 1$ with respect to $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Impact of d and z for SVD-SPF(+/-) model with $q = 1$

5.1.8. Parameter Analysis Additional Quantities

We note that the average number of neighbors for the parameter analysis, requiring at least 30 neighbors to make a recommendation, was 358.1. Further, we note that the average number of unique target items considered for recommendation, having been taken by the neighbors in the target semester, was 184.4. Additionally, we note that the average number of unique history courses, having been taken by the neighbors in the first semester, was 124.6. We note that this implies that the average matrix size for the HITS methods would be approximately 358×184 whereas the average matrix size for the SVD methods would be approximately 125×184 .

Table 11: Best models with respect to $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ from the parameter analysis.

Model	Parameters	$Recall(good)$	$Recall(bad)$	$Recall(diff)_{gb}$	$Recall(diff)_{pf}$	Matched
AVG	$c = 10$	0.275	0.15	0.125	0.058	553.3
HITS	$z = 3.7$ $\xi = 0.3$	0.432	0.386	0.046	0.061	1058.8
HITSW-PF(+)	$z = 3.3$ $\xi = 0.1$ $q = 3$ $v = +$	0.344	0.206	0.138	0.131	739.7
HITSW-PF(+/-)	$z = 3.3$ $\xi = 0.1$ $q = 1$ $v = +/-$	0.31	<u>0.145</u>	0.164	0.154	612.1
POP		0.463	0.487	-0.023	-0.029	<u>1203.3</u>
SVD-GB(+)	$v = +$ $d = 1$	0.451	0.399	0.051	0.025	1087.8
SVD-GB(++)	$v = ++$ $d = 1$	0.449	0.467	-0.018	-0.011	1156.4
SVD-GB(+/-)	$v = +/-$ $d = 100$	<u>0.494</u>	0.343	0.15	0.126	1107.5
SVD-PF(+)	$z = 3.7$ $v = +$ $d = 2$	0.434	0.332	0.102	0.093	997.3
SVD-PF(++)	$z = 0.0$ $v = ++$ $d = 1$	0.449	0.467	-0.018	-0.011	1156.4
SVD-PF(+/-)	$z = 3.3$ $v = +/-$ $d = 200$	0.371	0.204	0.167	<u>0.207</u>	779.2
SVD-SPF(+)	$z = 3.3$ $q = 3$ $v = +$ $d = 20$	0.38	0.207	<u>0.174</u>	0.185	792.5
SVD-SPF(++)	$z = 2.7$ $q = 4$ $v = ++$ $d = 30$	0.462	0.356	0.106	0.103	1071.2
SVD-SPF(+/-)	$z = 3.3$ $q = 4$ $v = +/-$ $d = 200$	0.332	0.163	0.169	0.195	678.0

Table 12: Best models with respect to $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ from the parameter analysis.

Model	Parameters	$Recall(passed)$	$Recall(failed)$	$Recall(diff)_{pf}$	$Recall(diff)_{gb}$	Matched
AVG	$c = 100$	0.217	0.152	0.065	0.009	561.9
HITS	$z = 3.7$ $\xi = 0.1$	0.421	0.358	0.062	0.046	1062.4
HITSW-PF(+)	$z = 3.0$ $\xi = 0.1$ $q = 4$ $v = +$	0.333	0.189	0.144	0.105	832.6
HITSW-PF(+)	$z = 3.0$ $\xi = 0.1$ $q = 4$ $v = +-$	0.31	0.144	0.166	0.11	770.6
POP		0.461	0.491	-0.029	-0.023	1203.3
SVD-GB(+)	$v = +$ $d = 200$	0.527	0.489	0.038	0.027	1346.5
SVD-GB(++)	$v = ++$ $d = 50$	<u>0.528</u>	0.533	-0.006	-0.034	<u>1366.5</u>
SVD-GB(+)	$v = +-$ $d = 200$	0.449	0.322	0.127	0.149	1108.9
SVD-PF(+)	$z = 4.0$ $v = +$ $d = 100$	0.473	0.36	0.113	0.08	1181.7
SVD-PF(++)	$z = 0.0$ $v = ++$ $d = 50$	0.528	0.533	-0.006	-0.034	1366.5
SVD-PF(+)	$z = 3.3$ $v = +-$ $d = 200$	0.321	<u>0.114</u>	0.207	<u>0.167</u>	779.2
SVD-SPF(+)	$z = 3.0$ $q = 4$ $v = +$ $d = 100$	0.396	0.193	0.203	0.134	967.1
SVD-SPF(++)	$z = 2.0$ $q = 4$ $v = ++$ $d = 50$	0.484	0.357	0.127	0.045	1211.5
SVD-SPF(+)	$z = 3.0$ $q = 4$ $v = +-$ $d = 100$	0.383	0.168	<u>0.215</u>	0.136	933.8

5.2. NEIGHBOR AND FILTERING EXPERIMENTS

We evaluate the best models from the parameter analysis with respect to $Recall(diff)_{pf}$, that is, the models corresponding to rows with the model (first) column highlighted in Table 12 under different neighbor and filtering circumstances. The minimum count of neighbors required for recommendation is set to vary over $[0, 10, 20, \dots, 200]$ for each experiment not using the global neighborhood. The three non global neighbor strategies are exact grade matching, letter grade matching, and exact grade matching with attributes (entry college). We conduct a fourth experiment where we utilize exact grade matching and apply the course filter for recommendation. Then, we evaluate all models from Table 12 with a global neighborhood, that is, allowing all students in the training set to be neighbors and no course filter.

5.2.1. Neighbor and Filtering Experiments Results

EXACT GRADE MATCHING The results for the experiment utilizing exact grade matching with varying minimum neighbor count and no course filter is given in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Varying Minimum Neighbor Count using Exact Grade Matching (Default) Neighbor Strategy

LETTER GRADE MATCHING The results for the experiment utilizing strict letter grade matching with varying minimum neighbor count and no course filter is given in Figure 9.

EXACT GRADE WITH ATTRIBUTE ENTRY COLLEGE The results for the experiment utilizing exact grade matching and attribute matching for entry college with varying minimum neighbor count and no course filter is given in Figure 10.

EXACT GRADE WITH COURSE FILTER The results for the experiment utilizing exact grade matching with the course filter applied for recommendation is given in Figure 11.

(a) $Recall(diff)_{pf}$

(b) Count Recommended Match Actual

Figure 9: Varying Minimum Neighbor Count using Letter Grade Matching Neighbor Strategy

(a) $Recall(diff)_{pf}$

(b) Count Recommended Match Actual

Figure 10: Varying Minimum Neighbor Count using Exact Grade Matching with Matching Attribute (Entry College) Neighbor Strategy

GLOBAL NEIGHBORHOOD The results for the experiment with a global neighborhood and no course filter is given in Figure 12. We note that the global neighborhood had an average neighbor count of 4788, average unique target course count of 673.1, and average history course count of 448.8.

Figure 11: Varying Minimum Neighbor Count using Exact Grade Matching Neighbor Strategy and Applying Course Filter

Figure 12: Results for a Global Neighborhood

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

6.1. PARAMETER ANALYSIS

We conduct a parameter analysis to get an idea of the best parameters to use for the comparative neighbor experiments. From the parameter analysis, we first notice that the parameters for the best models with respect to $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ in Table 11 are not the same when comparing with respect to $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ in Table 12 apart from the SVD-PF(+/-) model. One observation we make with regards to the metrics $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ and $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ is that the $Recall(diff)_{gb}$

metric seems to be slightly noisier than the metric $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ with respect to the considered models. In support, we observe the SVD models for $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ all have selected a value for d greater or equal to the parameter d for $Recall(diff)_{gb}$, with SVD-SPF(+/-) being the only exception. The higher values for d means we use more singular vector information, in that, the additional singular vector information continues to be useful. Hence, selecting a lower value for d may mean the constructed model is not fitting the problem well, or if the performance is good, the model is successfully capturing the required information and able to ignore the additional singular vector information. We note that the various considered SVD(+/-) models seem to fit well for both metrics. Further, we observe the best models for $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ all capture more matched courses that the best models for $Recall(diff)_{gb}$.

An interesting observation is the SVD-SPF(+) model performs similarly (and better/best with respect to $Recall(diff)_{gb}$) to the SVD-SPF(+/-) model whereas the other SVD(+) models do not perform similarly to other SVD(+/-) models. We note that this is due to the scaling by the passing rate which is nearly equivalent (when $q = 1$) to SVD-PF(+/-) with the difference being SVD-SPF(+) does not capture when fail counts exceed pass counts like in SVD-PF(+/-). We see that the scaling factor improves the model as SVD-SPF(+/-) outperforms SVD-PF(+/-). For the variations of the SVD models, we observe that the +/- models outperform the + models which outperform the ++ models with respect to $Recall(diff)_{pf}$.

For the HITS models, we observe that the HITS model is outperformed by the HITSW(+) model which is outperformed by the HITSW(+/-) model. Interestingly, the HITSW(+/-) model outperforms the SVD-GB(+/-) model despite using 2 singular vectors, one for the + matrix and one for the - matrix, whereas the SVD-GB(+/-) model uses 100-200 pairs (left and right) of singular vectors. Thus, we see that the construction of the matrix (matrices) used is very important. Further, in Figure 6, we see that ξ has almost no effect on the performance of the HITSW(+/-) model. We note that the parameter q is observed to have an effect for HITSW-PF(+/-) as the value (0.154) in Figure 6 for $q = 1, z = 3.0, \xi = 0.1$ is less than the value (0.166) for $q = 4, z = 3.0, \xi = 0.1$. This contrasts with the fact that q had negligible effect for SVD-SPF(+/-). Also, we see that the HITSW(+/-) model improves as z increases until a grade of 3.3 (B+) after which the model decreases in performance. We see a similar observation for SVD-SPF(+/-) in Figure 7. Further, for the SVD-SPF(+/-) model in Figure 7, we see that performance of the model increases as d increases as expected.

6.2. EXACT GRADE MATCHING

The first comparative experiment uses the best models from the parameter analysis to observe the impact of the exact grade matching neighbor strategy and the required neighbor count for recommendation with this strategy. Exact grade matching can be thought of as the default neighbor selection strategy for our purposes. For exact grade matching, we observe the order of the best models in Figure 8. Further, we note that the AVG model is nearly constant in performance because of the high value for c selected requiring many neighbors to have taken a course to consider its average. We observe that the ‘‘popularity’’ like models POP and HITS get better as n increases but the other models perform the same or worse as n increases. We also note the decrease in matched courses when n increases as expected as less students will get a recommendation and hence the ‘‘recommendation’’ will be unable to match taken courses.

6.3. LETTER GRADE MATCHING

The second comparative experiment uses the best models from the parameter analysis to observe the impact of the letter grade matching neighbor strategy and the required neighbor count for recommendation with this strategy. Since letter grade matching is a relaxation of exact grade matching, we might expect a much better result than the result using exact grade matching. However, it appears letter grade matching in Figure 9 does not differ much from exact grade matching. We note that this is likely because +, - grades that can additionally be matched for exact grade matching are used much less frequently than the strict letter grades. We do notice that the average model has slightly shifted, and the match counts seem to decrease more slowly as n increases as compared to the exact grade matching.

6.4. EXACT GRADE MATCHING WITH ATTRIBUTE MATCHING

The third comparative experiment uses the best models from the parameter analysis to observe the impact of the exact grade matching with attributes neighbor strategy and the required neighbor count for recommendation with this strategy. By adding additional information to the neighbor matching strategy such as entry college, we might expect a better recommendation using our metrics. However, we observe that the neighbor selection strategy using attributes leads to matching less courses as n increases in Figure 10. We note that using just one broad attribute, that of matching entry college (6 values for 5 college designations and no college designation), causes the models to recommend less relevant courses for larger values of n with less courses being matched and metric performance being subsequently worse (due to less courses being matched).

6.5. EXACT GRADE MATCHING WITH COURSE FILTER

The fourth comparative experiment uses the best models from the parameter analysis to observe the impact of the using the course filter. For using the course filter, we hope to not remove too many of the relevant courses. We observe slightly less courses being matched for exact grade matching when applying the course filter in Figure 11. Overall, the performance does not seem to have decreased much and the number of matched courses seems to have only decreased slightly.

6.6. GLOBAL NEIGHBORHOOD

Lastly, we conduct a comparative experiment using a global neighborhood to see how the models perform without specific neighbor considerations and compare the result with the “local” neighborhood methods. For the global neighborhood experiment in Figure 12, we see that all of the models have decreased in performance compared to the “local” neighborhood methods. We do observe that SVD-GB(+/-) outperforms HITSW(+/-) for the global neighborhood experiment but note the advantage of the SVD methods, in that, the profile is still computed for each student based on historical courses (different recommendations for each student) whereas HITSW(+/-) provides the same recommendation for every student based on the global neighborhood. Overall, the order of the methods using the global neighborhood is the same as for the order of the methods using the “local” neighborhood methods or comparing with the parameter analysis in Table 12.

6.7. LIMITATIONS

We note that our study is limited in that course recommendation is only considered for the second semester of the first year whereas recommendation for other semesters could be considered. Further, our models are only compared with the SVD model from [Morsy and Karypis \(2019b\)](#), and other recommendation models could be considered. The choice of evaluation metrics is a limitation of our study whereas other evaluation metrics could be considered or may be desired depending on the task at hand.

It should be noted that course recommendation is “high stakes” and certain analytic interventions have been observed to have “unintended consequences” such as a decrease in GPA ([Jiang et al., 2019](#); [Jayaprakash et al., 2014](#)). Thus, any use of analytical tools for assisting in decision making should be carefully considered.

6.8. CONCLUSIONS

To assist in the problem of course recommendation, we introduced the $Recall(diff)_{pf}$ metric similar to the $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ metric and utilized different neighborhood methods and a course filtering strategy to examine our models in different contexts. In summary, we have constructed the HITS, HITSW, SVD-PF, and SVD-SPF recommenders. The HITSW recommenders improved upon the constructed HITS recommenders by correcting the popularity bias of the HITS recommenders. Then, we observed that HITSW(+/-) outperformed SVD-GB(+/-) from the literature even though HITSW uses far fewer singular vectors than SVD-GB. As the SVD recommenders can more easily use more singular vector information, we constructed the SVD-PF recommender using the idea of pass/fail course counts instead of good/bad course counts. Then, we scaled the count matrices, using ideas from the HITSW scaling, in an extension of SVD-PF to create the SVD-SPF recommender. We observed that the SVD-SPF(+/-) recommender outperforms the SVD-PF(+/-) recommender which outperforms the HITSW(+/-) recommender. Overall, the SVD-SPF(+/-) recommender outperforms the SVD-GB(+/-) recommender by approximately 13% and 69% with respect to metrics $Recall(diff)_{gb}$ and $Recall(diff)_{pf}$, respectively. Finally, we have provided the intuition behind the model improvements and suggested possible extensions for further study, in that, different kernels or feature maps may be explored for the HITSW methods which may then be carried over to other methods.

7. DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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9. SUPPORTING MATERIALS

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